

Designing for Enduring Product Relationships

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Abstract: How can we design products that forge durable emotional connections with their users? This paper takes a close look at human-product interactions, and uses this information to identify four important design principles that can help facilitate user engagement and attachment. A product that facilitates meaningful interactions with users, is capable of changing and evolving through use, actively responds to its environment, and awakens memories through sensory inputs will form a stronger emotional attachment with its user than a static, inanimate one. Understanding the dynamic properties of materials and technology, and integrating them appropriately into a product's design will engender the formation of sustainable and emotionally engaging connections. Designing for enduring human-object relationships requires that we step away from the constraints of industry and create new models of production, consumption, and repair that support the longevity of our attachments with these objects.

Key words: *Relationships, Sensory Engagement, Responsiveness, Meaningful Interactions, Evolution.*

1. Introduction

Today's design industry is focused upon providing new products that are smaller, faster, different, better. Our capitalistic society has placed a high level of importance upon the industrial model of continuous production, where how much we produce in a year, the Gross National Product (GNP), dictates our success as a country. Jonathan Chapman, author of the book *Emotionally Durable Design*, suggests that we have designed away the more poetic and enduring characteristics of material culture, by focusing on producing the next "hot product". To create sustainable relationships with consumers, Chapman suggests that products must begin to exhibit more diverse, dynamic and multifaceted characteristics. [1] Products should engage consumers at an emotional level, meeting their needs not just for the moment, but also for a much longer period of time. By stimulating emotional bonding between consumers and their products we can increase the lifespan of products, which will contribute to the creation of a more sustainable society by decreasing resource consumption and unnecessary waste. [2] So how do we design products that engage with the emotions of their users? This paper investigates human-product attachments in order to define a set of design principles for creating emotionally engaging products.

2. Research

Trust, diversity, respect, varied interaction, and effective communication are core components of any successful human relationship. It can be argued then that products must be able to fulfill these same characteristics in order to form a similar emotional bond with the consumer. According to Donald Norman, "fake emotions look fake," because as humans, we are very good at detecting false attempts to manipulate us whether its coming from another human or one of the computer systems we interact with on a daily basis. [3] As a result, if an object

performs its function poorly or expresses incongruent emotional qualities, as consumers we become irritated and disillusioned with the product, quickly moving on to an alternative we hope will perform better.

In order to engage its users in a sincere and honest relationship, an object's characteristics must correspond to the functions and roles that it plays in our lives. Hekkert and Desmet recommend that whatever the desired user experience is, it should be defined before the product is designed. Adding emotional qualities onto an existing product is a superficial solution that often results in major incongruities between a product's function and use. [4] Additionally, a product should do more than just deliver a bundle of functional features and benefits. According to Hassenzahl, customers want products that "dazzle their senses, touch their hearts and stimulate their minds." [5] Individuals express themselves through physical objects so a product needs to communicate identity, in addition to being stimulating and provoking memories. However, while there is a human need for novelty, change, and self-expression through objects, a product must first provide functionality before being appreciated for its emotional qualities. [5, 6]

Enduring human-human attachments have purpose, depth, and are filled with shared stories and memories. Research into human-product attachment has shown that after owning a product for a year, the user's interest and attachment to it begin to wane. Interestingly, the highest level of attachment was found for products owned over 20 years, indicating that similar to human relationships, shared memories significantly enhance an individual's level of attachment. While personal enjoyment may be the primary reason people become attached to new products, the stories and memories associated with the product may be the primary reason why individuals become attached to and keep products they have owned for a long time, even when they have lost their original functionality. [2]

Hekkert and Desmet suggest that there are three components to an individual's experience of a product: aesthetic pleasure, attribution of meaning, and emotional response. An object's capacity to delight one or more of our sensory modalities (aesthetic), form profound and sustained attachments with us, and be interpreted as beneficial, detrimental, or inconsequential to the user's established position in relation to their environment, defines its product experience. [7] Using human interactions and relationships as a guide, the following design case investigates the role that four physical characteristics (sensory engagement, responsivity, meaningful interactions, and product evolution) play in the product experience, with the end-goal of identifying a core set of design principles that can help facilitate the creation of emotionally engaging products.

2.1. Sensory Engagement

Humans are sensory creatures, and we use various combinations of our senses to inform us about our surroundings and our companions. Our sense of smell, sound, and touch play as important a role in understanding our environment and forming attachments as vision does, despite the fact that many designers design solely for the visual appeal of a product. Japanese designer, Kenya Hara believes that heightening the senses and blending them through design will provide us with a truer, more direct experience of the world, something that modern technology has diminished. [8] Technology is becoming increasingly hands-off (embedded) and visual, limiting our ability to connect and comprehend a product's functionality through our other senses. Designing for these other senses can provide users with a deep holistic understanding of the product, while ignoring them can lead to an emotional disconnect.

Multi-sensory engagement necessitates a holistic design process, where designers are involved in hands-on prototyping of products in order to fully understand how they will live in the world. Additionally, it requires comprehensive material and technology exploration to pair sensory stimuli with function. Not only can materials provide tactile clues about a product's function, but they can also trigger memories through sensory recognition. It is possible to highlight the subtle differences between recalled memories and reality through an object's design, allowing the user to understand and connect with a product at a deeper, emotional level. One example of a design that awakens memories through stimulation is Naoto Fukasawa's Juice Skins (Figure 1). Fukasawa's juice boxes both visually and tactilely represent the flavor of juice they contain. The user instinctively responds to the shape, color, and texture of the juice container, pulling from their previous experiences with fruit to understand the juice box and its contents at a physical level. An emotional connection is forged between the user and the containers because the sensory characteristics of the object are completely aligned with its function and the role it plays in their lives.

Figure 1. Naoto Fukasawa's Strawberry Juice Skin [9]

2.2. Responsiveness

Communication plays a significant role in all human relationships. We engage in constant dialogue with other individuals, using language (both vocal and body) to express our emotions and opinions as well as respond to those of others. The reciprocal nature of these interactions keeps us emotionally engaged, and the same holds true for our interactions with products. In fact, the static nature of many everyday objects inhibits them from having an active presence in our lives. By designing responsive elements into an object's function, we allow a dialogue to open up between the user and the product about its conditions of use.

New technologies and materials are becoming increasingly capable of recognizing and responding to changing conditions. One product that exemplifies responsive design is the Hanabi light by Studio Nendo (Figure 2). Hanabi is made of a heat-sensitive metal alloy with shape memory properties that are activated when the light

bulb is switched on, resulting in the petals of the shade opening. Hanabi utilizes new technology to animate its form, allowing it to open up when lit, and close when turned off. The responsive behavior of the light triggers our memory of flowers blooming, and we instinctively engage with the Hanabi light at a deeper emotional level.

Figure 2. Nendo's Hanabi Lamp [10]

While the Hanabi light functions only in response to the user switching it on and off, Shi Yuan's thermochromic wallpaper takes a different approach by actively responding to its environmental conditions without the need of user interaction (Figure 3). The wallpaper, a product that ordinarily fades into the background of a room, has been altered so that it can "bloom" colored flowers when exposed to different degrees of heat. In Figure 3 the heater is pictured giving off a low level of heat so that only the paper in its close proximity is affected, however, one can imagine on a hot summer day the entire room would be covered in pink flowers. This simple alteration not only applies dynamic characteristics to the walls, but it also begins to inform its users about the changing conditions of the environment they inhabit, engaging them in a conversation about heat and temperature.

Figure 3. Shi Yuan's Heat Sensitive Wallpaper [11]

2.3. Meaningful Interactions

The ability of an object to facilitate meaningful interactions with its user is critical to its ability to connect at an emotional level with him or her. The human emotional system plays an essential role in survival, social-interaction and cooperation, and learning. Therefore, characteristics of successful human-human interactions can be used to inform human-objects interactions.

One example of a designed object that addresses these issues is found in Dunne and Raby's Technological Dreams Series, No. 1, Robots. In this series, Robot 3: Sentinel is an object that requires a retinal scan to allow

the user access their stored private data (Figure 4). However, instead of the quick scan one expects from a retinal scanner, this robot demands that the user stare into its eyes for a prolonged period of time. Not only is the user required to hold eye contact with the object, she also must hold it in her arms for it to be able to “see” her. Both these actions, prolonged eye contact and arm cradling, are examples of meaningful human-human interactions. By incorporating these actions into a product’s functionality, Dunne and Raby have designed a product experience that is understandable and emotionally valuable to its user. Interestingly, this emotional connection comes at the expense of efficiency and speed, suggesting that the principles of smaller, faster, different and better are not necessarily the best to follow when designing for enduring product relationships.

Figure 4. Dunne and Raby’s Robot 3: Sentinel [12]

2.4. Evolution

Humans are dynamic creatures, with personalities that are constantly evolving. As a result, our long-term relationships are characterized by having the ability to adapt to these changes over time. If we desire our products to have a similar longevity in our lives, they must possess the ability to change and evolve through their continued use. Many objects wear down over time through use. For example, pots and pans get banged and burned, plates get chipped and broken. However, as much we may complain about these marks, dents, and stains, they also make the objects personal. These visible reminders of use and repair all contain a story, and it is these shared stories that connect us to our products and make them special. [4] Unfortunately few products are designed to degrade gracefully and grow old along with their owners, despite the fact that this kind of personalization carries a huge emotional significance, and enriches our lives. As designers, we must begin to understand what it means to design for longevity and think about the future needs and uses of the products we are sending out into the world.

One example of a product that embraces the “wearing in” process is Kristine Bjaadal’s Underskog Furniture Textile (Figure 5). At the time of purchase, the furniture’s upholstery presents as deep blue velvet. However, as the user wears down the fabric through daily use, the velvet begins to reveal that it has a deeper layer of design, i.e. a satin floral pattern hidden beneath the pile of the velvet. The visibility of the pattern depends on light and viewing angle, which allows the textile to continue changing and surprising even after the velvet piling wears off. In this way the furniture’s appearance evolves over time, and the story of its use becomes visible, tangible, and

tied to the memories of its user. Kristine Bjaadal embraced the aging process in her design through her careful consideration of material properties and combinations. Allowing products to evolve with their users also requires them to be designed for disassembly, so that they can be repaired or updated. Ultimately, the products that endure are those that have become unique through their interactions with their users, something designers should consider when choosing their materials and product finishes.

Figure 5. Kristine Bjaadal's Underskog Furniture Textile [13]

3. Conclusions

Each product highlighted in this design case uniquely demonstrates how material and technological choices made by the designer can impact the emotional engagement of a product. Understanding the dynamic properties of materials and technologies, and integrating them appropriately into a product's design, is central to the formation of sustainable and satisfying connections with products. Designing objects that exhibit the physical characteristics described above requires that we step away from the demands of our consumption driven culture and rethink our approach to creating new products. If a product is designed to express the attributes of a successful relationship, it opens the door for emotional attachments to be formed, and a new set of values to be placed upon that object. The need to design for repair becomes imperative since individuals will desire continued interaction with the same object, and the impetus to discard the old to purchase the new will be eliminated. When emphasis shifts from designing the new-next-best to the upkeep and maintenance of cherished objects, new models of production and consumption will arise.

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